

The Role of Inorganic Salts on the TiO₂ based Photocatalysis of Rodamin B (RB) in Aqueous Solutions

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Abstract

The photo-catalytic bleaching of industrial dyes using TiO₂ has appeared promising in laboratory studies, but little attention has been focused on whether other species might be found in wastewater have a harmful or useful effects on the photo-bleaching. This study highlights effects of some ionic species on the photo-bleaching of Rodamin B (RB) dye in the aqueous acidic and basic solutions. The rate of RB photo-catalytic oxidation was studied at different pH values. The effect of solvents on photo-degradation of RB was also investigated. Various metals doped titanium dioxide (TiO₂) photocatalysis have been studied intensively for the photodegradation of dye in wastewater treatment. The Ag particles were photodeposited on TiO₂ powder surface. Nanostructure Ag-TiO₂ nanoparticles were synthesized by photo reduction method. The X-ray diffraction (XRD), Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM), Energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDXS), and photoluminescence (PL) spectrophotometry were applied to investigate the structure and morphologies of the samples. It was found that the loaded Ag particles have no effect on the XRD patterns. Photodegradation capacity of TiO₂ nanoparticles was compared to Ag-TiO₂ photoactivity. Above the optimum silver ion loading, the activity of Ag/TiO₂ particles decreased. The use of electron acceptors, such as S₂O₈²⁻ in TiO₂ system increased dye photo-degradation.

Keywords: Photo catalytic oxidation; TiO₂; Rodamin B; Ionic species

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Introduction

Rhodamine dyes (RB) are important class of xanthene dyes. They have high quantum yield of fluorescence and high absorption factors. They have been widely studied due to their properties and practical applications in dye lasers [1]. Furthermore, RB dyes have been used for some specific applications, such as biological stains, electrochemical luminescence sensitizer, water-tracing agents, molecular probes, chromo-ionophores in optical chemical sensors and solar collectors and many others devices so treatment extra dye in wastewater is very important [2]. Clearly, wastewater is full of different material with different range of the pH values. Photo-degradation efficiency of dyes is affected by pH of the solution in the presence of TiO₂.

Heterogeneous photo-catalysis is a processing which the irradiation of an oxide semi-conductor produces photo-excited electrons (e⁻) and positive charged holes (h⁺) to the form

hydroxyl radical and superoxide radical anion, that both of them play as the oxidizing species in the photo-catalytic oxidation method. The efficiency of photo-excitation of the semi-conductor is dependent on the energy state of the electrons valence band and conduction band. The extent of dye adsorption depends on several factors such as, dye nature of the dye, surface area of the used photo-catalyst, concentration and pH of the solution. The pH controls the surface charge of the photo-catalyst and dye. Adsorption of the dye is minimum when the pH of the solution is at the isoelectric point (point of zero charge). The surface of the photo-catalyst is positively charged below isoelectric point and carries a negative charge above that. As a result, the structure of dye is important to be found in due course, i.e., the efficiency of adsorption on the surface of a photo-catalyst can be low or high in acidic and basic media [3].

In TiO₂/UV system positive charged holes can be scavenged by the negatively charged anions and therefore depends on the

positive charged or negatively charged adsorption of dyes on the surface of TiO_2 is considerably inhibited or promoted [4]. Previous studies indicated that inorganic anions can scavenge $\bullet\text{OH}$ to form the corresponding anion radicals [5-7]. The anion radicals may themselves oxidize organic and inorganic compounds [5,8,9], which can also influence on the total rates of the photo-catalytic oxidation. It is also reported that competitive adsorption of the inorganic anions for active sites on the TiO_2 surface may contribute to the photo-catalytic degradation of organic compounds [10-13]. For instance, Cl^- decreases the degradation rate of 2-chlorophenol and 2-nitrophenol at pH values lower than the TiO_2 point of zero charge (pHpzc), while Cl^- had no inhibitory role at pH values greater than the pHpzc due to slight adsorption to the negatively charged TiO_2 surface [12]. Inorganic anions can also change the rates of dye photo-catalytic oxidation in one of the following ways: (i) $\bullet\text{OH}$ scavenging by inorganic anions, (ii) direct oxidation of dye by anion radicals, or (iii) adsorption of inorganic anions to the TiO_2 surface [14,15].

The photo-catalytic activity of TiO_2 for the oxidative degradation of (RB) may be enhanced by first, surface modification using metals, second, transition metal doping and third, coupled photo-catalysts. In this research Ag metals were used for increasing in photo-degradation of (RB) dyes. Improving the photocatalytic activity by Ag deposition may be associated to different mechanisms: (1) Ag nanoparticles deposited on TiO_2 act as electron traps, enhancing the electron-hole separation and the later transfer of the trapped electron to the adsorbed O_2 acting as an electron acceptor [1-3].

(2) self-photosensitization pathway, that means, extend the light absorption into the visible range and enhance surface electron excitation by plasmon resonances excited by visible light, injecting an electron into the conduction band of the TiO_2 semiconductor, so, the injected electron on the TiO_2 particle reacts with adsorbed oxidants to produce reactive oxygen radicals and dye is degraded by these oxygen radicals. Under visible light irradiation, the semiconductor TiO_2 acts only as an electron-transfer mediator and

(3) modify the surface properties of photocatalyst [4-8]. Zakerhamidi and co-author studied solvent effects on the dipole moment and photophysical properties of rhodamine dyes. This study describes the effective parameters such as pH of the solution, type of solvent and cationic and anionic species on the photo-bleaching of (RB) in the presence of TiO_2 nanoparticles [16,17]. The amount of degradation of RB were discussed in different circumstances. In this experience it was investigated the effects of pH and common salts and solvent on photo degradation of dye Rhodamine (RB).

Materials and Methods

Titanium dioxide nanoparticles (purity >99.5 %,) with average particle size 30 nm and specific surface of 50 m^2/g was purchased from Degussa Corporation (USA).

Compounds of $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Al}(\text{NO}_3)_3$, $\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, $\text{Fe}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and FeCl_2 were

obtained from Fluka (Buchs, Switzerland) and used without further purification. The pH (2,6 and 12) values of the solutions were adjusted using HCl (0.01 M) and KOH (0.01 M) solutions. RB dye (10^{-5} M) was prepared from Fluka (Buchs, Switzerland). The photo-catalyst was added to dye solution and the suspension was irradiated under UV-Vis light. Then fluorescence spectra of the dye solutions were recorded and de-colorization process was monitored in terms of change in intensity at λ_{max} excitation (550 nm) and λ_{max} emission (580 nm) of the dye after 0, 2, 5, 8, 10 minute irradiation.

Ag- TiO_2 was synthesized by photo-reduction of AgNO_3 . In this way, Ag^+ ions are deposited as Ag metal on the TiO_2 surface by photo-reduction of AgNO_3 under UV irradiation [8]. One gram of TiO_2 was added into 250 mL of double-distilled water and then irradiated with UV-Vis light for 10 min to remove any impurities present on TiO_2 surface. Then appropriate amount of AgNO_3 was added into the suspension of TiO_2 solution and the suspension adjusted to pH 3.5, finally it was irradiated using UV light for 40 min with continuous stirring under N_2 atmosphere. The suspension was then filtered, washed, dried and then ground into a fine powder [9,10].

General procedure

The photo-catalytic reaction was carried out in an inner irradiation type reactor. The photo-catalyst powder was dispersed by magnetic stirrer. A 300 W high-pressure mercury lamp from Oriol GMBH, Model 8500 (Cheltenham, England) was used as the light source and spectro-fluorimeter of Perkin-Elmer LS-3B Luminescence (USA) was used. The cell was made with Quartz (3 mL content) that it was put it in the close space in front of the light in reactor. Analysis of the crystalline structures was performed by XRD Diffractometer (GBC MMA made in Australia) with wavelength of Cu K α radiation in 2θ range from 15° to 80° , SEM analysis was performed by a VEGA TESCAN (USA) instrument.

Results

The effect of pH

To study the effect of pH on photo-degradation, several experiments were done using 1.0×10^{-5} M dye concentration and it was exposed under UV-Vis light in the presence of nanoparticles of TiO_2 . **Figure 1** shows increasing of % degradation of RB in acidic (pH=2), normal (ca. pH=6) and basic medium (ca. pH=12) with increasing of anionic species, after ten minute UV-Vis irradiation in every experiments and in present of 0.1 g/L titanium dioxide. As can be seen acidic, normal and basic medium is significantly depended on the concentration of anions either NO_3^- or Cl^- . The behavior of dye degradation in acidic, normal and basic medium are nearly the same so that in higher concentration of anions the percentage of dye degradation as function of anion concentration is smooth (**Figure 1**).

Figure 1: Effect of anions on the %degradation of RB under UV-Vis irradiation for 5 min at the present of 0.1 g/L titanium dioxide, in acidic (■), normal (♦) and basic (5) medium (a) Cl⁻ and (b) NO₃⁻.

Effect of cations on the titanium dioxide-based photo-catalytic oxidation of aqueous R

Wastewater is full of material, effect anion and cation for increase adsorption dye on catalyst was investigated in different pH, however the kind of cation is important. Salts of NO₃⁻ and Cl⁻ are very common. In a quartz cell, 3 mL of the solution containing 0.01 M of (a) NO₃⁻ and (b) Cl⁻ are exposed by UV-V irradiation for five minutes in the presence of 0.1 g/L titanium dioxide. Experiments were performed using 50 mL of solution with constant initial concentration of dye RB (10⁻⁵ M) and in the present of salts nitrate and chloride. **Figure 2** shows the effect of cations on % degradation of RB in normal medium with increasing of anionic species. The counter ions are the same, i.e., (a) NO₃⁻ and (b) Cl⁻ for the cations of Al³⁺, Cu²⁺ and Co²⁺ and Fe³⁺. **Figure 2** illustrates the influence of the cations on the % degradation of RB. Results reveal that % degradation of RB is highly enhance in the presence of Fe²⁺ and in contrast the degradation is very low in the presence of Cu²⁺. The other cations (Al³⁺, Co²⁺) are also have differences effects, in this case both cations of Al³⁺, Co²⁺ have almost similar effect on the % degradation of RB so that % degradation almost have the nearly the same values. The order

of % degradation for the cations are as follows Fe³⁺ > Co²⁺ > Al³⁺ > Cu²⁺ (**Figure 2**).

Figure 2: Effect of caions on the % degradation of RB under UV-Vis irradiation for 5 min at the present of 0.1 g/L titanium dioxide. (a) NO₃⁻ and (b) Cl⁻.

Effect of solvent

The percentage of dye degradation was also examined using different of solvents i.e., water, methanol and ethanol. **Figure 3** illustrate the effect of dye degradation in aqueous (water) and nonaqueous (alcoholic medium). Results indicated that rate of % degradation in water is the highest amount (**Figure 3**).

Figure 3: Effect of solvents on the %degradation of RB under UV-Vis irradiation for 5 min at the present of 0.1 g/L titanium dioxide, in ethanol (■), water (♦) and methanol (5) medium.

Characterization of TiO₂ and Ag-TiO₂ nanoparticles

In order to investigate the changes in the crystal structure due to silver deposit, XRD measurements were taken in the range of 2θ 15-80 for pure TiO₂ and Ag-TiO₂ nanoparticles (**Figure 1**). It is seen that the XRD patterns of Ag-TiO₂ sample are almost the same as for pure TiO₂, except for the intensities of the peaks. Also, the XRD patterns show no diffraction peaks due to silver deposition. This may be due to the fact that deposition alters the crystallinity but not the crystal structure of Ag-TiO₂ and thus suggest that the silver deposits are merely placed on the surface of the crystals. Diffractions that are attributable to anatase phase of TiO₂ crystals

are clearly detectable at 2θ 25 [10, 11] (Figure 4).

Figure 4: XRD patterns for TiO₂ nanotubes and AgTiO₂.

Figure 2 shows the PL spectra of unloaded and loaded TiO₂ samples. The signal intensity of unloaded sample is very strong and shows evident characteristics of the radiative recombinations of electrons and holes. The PL peak at 367 nm arises from the band-to-band recombination which evidently decreases with the loaded Ag particles. Two factors affect the PL intensity after Ag deposition. One is the migration of the electrons from TiO₂ to Ag particles; the other is the Ag plasmon absorption. The PL band from 390 to 440 nm is from the recombination transition related to the surface structure, which also decreases with the loaded Ag, indicating the photo-deposited Ag has affected the surface structure of TiO₂, leading to the decrease of surface recombination but if silver amount became above the optimum loading, silver particles can also act as recombination centers so the signal intensity of loaded sample is very strong [11, 12] (Figure 5).

Figure 5: The PL spectra of unloaded and loaded TiO₂ samples.

Figure 2 shows SEM images of the AgTiO₂ composites. The general morphology of the AgTiO₂ can be clearly observed in these micrographs. TiO₂ particles were uniformly distributed. It can be considered that the better dispersion provides a larger number of active catalytic centers for the photocatalytic reaction (Figure 6).

Figure 6: SEM images of AgTiO₂ composites.

Figure 4 shows the results of elemental analysis from the EDX spectra of AgTiO₂ with 23, 45 at % weight of Ag composites. These spectra show the presence of peaks from Ag and Ti. The elemental composition analysis of the composite series is listed in Tables. Ti was the major elements in the composite series. Figure 7a is 23 at % weight of Ag composites and Figure 7b is 45 at % weight of Ag composites. As expected, it was observed that the Ag content of the AgTiO₂ composites showed an increase with increasing the at % weight of Ag (Figure 7).

Figure 7: The results of elemental analysis from the EDX spectra of AgTiO₂ with (a) 23, and (b) 45 at% weight of Ag composites.

Photo-catalytic degradation of RB

Figure 5 shows the change in the intensity of fluorescans spectra of RB (1.0 × 10⁵ M) in the presence of the TiO₂ and Ag-TiO₂ nanoparticles (100 mg/L) as photo-catalyst. After irradiation with UV-Vis light, the intensity of spectra decreased due to decolouration of the dye. Figure 5 indicated that speed of decolouration, after 5 min irradiation in present of AgTiO₂ was faster than in present of TiO₂ (Figure 8).

Figure 8: Shows the change in the intensity of fluorescans spectra of RB (1.0×10^5 M) in the presence of the TiO_2 and Ag- TiO_2 nanoparticles (100 mg/L) as photo-catalyst.

Effect of catalyst amount

The effect of Ag- TiO_2 amount on the photo-catalytic degradation of RB was studied at fixed concentration of RB M in aqueous solutions. **Figure 6** shows the photo-degradation efficiency of RB (% E) as a function of the amount of at % weight of Ag composites. An optimum silver ion loading of 23 at % weight of Ag was found. For all silver ion loadings used, Ag/ TiO_2 performed significantly better than bare TiO_2 . Above the optimum silver ion loading, the activity of Ag/ TiO_2 particles decreased. There are several reasons for the existence of an optimum metal loading. It is also possible that above the optimum loading, silver particles can also act as recombination centres [5,6,13] (**Figure 9**).

Figure 9: Shows the photo-degradation efficiency of RB (% E) as a function of the amount of at % weight of Ag composites.

Effect of electron acceptors in dye photo-degradation

The use of inorganic oxidants, such as $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ in TiO_2 system increased the quantum efficiencies either by inhibiting electron-hole pair recombination through scavenging conduction band electron at the surface of TiO_2 or by offering additional oxygen atom as an electron acceptor to from the superoxide radical ion and along reaction electron acceptor with Ag TiO_2 due production of active radicals. **Figure 7** gives the effect of electron acceptors in photo-catalytic activity of Ag TiO_2 . Dye exposed under UV-Vis for 2 min, (a) in present only Ag $\text{TiO}_2=0.12$ g/lit, (b) In present $\text{TiO}_2=0.1$

g/lit and in present of $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}=1 \times 10^{-3}$ M [10] (**Figure 10**).

Figure 10: The effect of electron acceptors in photo-catalytic activity of Ag TiO_2 . Dye exposed under UV - Vis for 2 min, (a) in present only Ag $\text{TiO}_2 = 0.12$ g/lit, (b) In present $\text{TiO}_2 = 0.1$ g/lit and in present of $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-} = 1 \times 10^{-3}$ M.

Discussion

The effect of pH

The pH of the solution is an important parameter which strongly influences the surface charge properties in aqueous dispersion. Generally, surface of the net TiO_2 is positively charged in acid media and negatively charged in alkaline media with an isoelectric point of around pH 6~7 [18]. Therefore, adsorbates in the aqueous solution tend to adsorb on the surface of TiO_2 by the negatively charged or electron abundant group in acidic solution and by positive charged in alkaline solution because of the electrostatic interaction [19]. The ζ -potential of TiO_2 with different pH amounts was investigated before. Photo-degradation efficiency of dyes is affected by pH of the solution in the presence of TiO_2 . The amount of pH solution changes the surface charge of TiO_2 particle [3]. As a result, the adsorption of dye on the surface is altered thus causing a change in the reaction rate. Under acidic or alkaline condition the surface of TiO_2 can be protonated or deprotonated (Eq. 1 and 2) respectively according to the following reactions, therefore, the pH effect is often dependent on the nature of the dye. To study the effect of pH on photo-degradation, several experiments were done using 1.0×10^{-5} M dye concentration and it was exposed under UV-Vis light in the presence of nanoparticles of TiO_2 [20]. **Figure 1** shows increasing of % degradation of RB in acidic (pH=2), normal (ca. pH=6) and basic medium (ca. pH=12) with increasing of anionic species, after ten minute UV-Vis irradiation in every experiments and in present of 0.1 g/lit Titanium dioxide. **Figure 1** shows the effect of anions (i.e., NO_3^- and Cl^-) on the % degradation of RB under UV-Vis irradiation (for 5 min) at the present of 0.1 g/L titanium dioxide in acidic, normal and basic medium. As can be seen acidic, normal and basic medium is significantly depended on the concentration of anions either NO_3^- or Cl^-). The behavior of dye degradation in acidic, normal and basic medium are nearly the same so that in higher concentration of anions the percentage of dye degradation as function of anion concentration is smooth. It is pertinent to point out that in both normal and basic medium the concentration of anion at concentration of about 25 mg/L

has lowest value of degradation either in the presence of NO_3^- or Cl^- . Results also revealed that the % degradation of RB is hardly depends on the concentration of anion concentration in acidic media. As a result the % degradation of RB is depended on medium, i.e., acid, neutral and basic. This evidence can be attributed to the surface of nanoparticles as well as the chemical structure of the dye in question.

Acidic medium

In acidic medium, the rationale behind this is that at low pH values, more H^+ are available for adsorption to mask the surface of the catalyst thus inhibiting the photo-excitation of semiconductor particles, [3]. In addition, adsorption of dye on the surface positively charged of TiO_2 is not favorite, results indicated that adsorption of RB on TiO_2 is significantly increased in the presence of the anionic species in acidic medium and hence increasing RB % degradation. **Figure 11** shows theoretically suggestions for increasing adsorption of RB on TiO_2 in the presence of the anion species (Cl^- or NO_3^-) in acidic solution with 10^{-2} molar of HCl with different concentrations of salt (**Figure 11**).

Figure 11 : Theoretically suggestions for increasing adsorption of RB on TiO_2 in the presence of the anion species (Cl^- or NO_3^-) in acidic solution, a no salt, b has moderate concentration and c with higher concentration than b.

Neutral medium

In neutral solution, the pH value of the reaction solutions under the experiment conditions was controlled at about 6, in which the surface of TiO_2 was positively charged. The acid dissociation constant of the carboxyl group of RB is about 4.1 ± 0.1 . Thus, under the experimental conditions, most of the carboxyl group of RB was dissociated and negatively charged at $-\text{COO}^-$ state and RB tends to adsorb on the surface positively charged of TiO_2

by the negatively charged carboxyl group of RB [19]. So rate of photo degradation of dye (RB) without salt in neutral medium is the highest. Therefore, RB Dye is zwitter-ionic form when the solution pH is higher than the acid dissociation constant of RB [21]. Adsorption of RB molecules through the positively charged significantly increased in the presence of the anionic species in normal medium. **Figure 12** shows theoretically suggest ions for increasing adsorption of RB on TiO_2 in the presence of the anionic species (Cl^- or NO_3^-) in normal medium (**Figure 12**).

Figure 12: Theoretically suggestions for increasing adsorption of RB on TiO_2 in the presence of the anionic species (Cl^- or NO_3^-) in normal medium, a no salt, b has moderate concentration and c with higher concentration than b.

Basic medium

In basic solution, RB is zwitter-ionic and the surface of TiO_2 is negatively charged. As a result, adsorption of RB molecules through the positively charged is chosen on the surface negatively charged of TiO_2 . Besides H_2O_2 molecules that are formed during photo-degradation process could easily self-decomposed in basic medium. The species of $\bullet\text{OOH}$ could also react with both $\bullet\text{OH}$ radical as well as H_2O_2 in the basic medium. Thus, it would decrease the concentration of $\bullet\text{OH}$ radicals and affect degradation efficiency of RB. The degradation rate was found to increase with oxidation potential of $\bullet\text{OH}$ radical in the acidic medium as reported by Wang additionally in the alkaline conditions there is a competitive adsorption between hydroxyl groups and the dye molecule [3,22,23].

It is pertinent to point out that the adsorption of RB molecules through the negatively charged carboxyl group on the surface negatively charged of TiO_2 was also significantly increased in the presence of the cationic species in basic medium. Results indicated that positively copper complex, leads to increase adsorption of RB on TiO_2 and hence increasing color removal from the solution. **Figure 13** shows theoretically suggest ions for increasing adsorption of RB on TiO_2 in the presence of the cation species Cu^{+2} in basic medium using 10^{-2} M of KOH with different concentrations of salt (**Figure 13**).

Figure 13: Theoretically suggestions for increasing adsorption of RB on TiO₂ in the presence of the cation species Cu²⁺ in basic medium, a no salt, b has moderate concentration and c with higher concentration than b.

Effect of cations on the titanium dioxide-based photo-catalytic oxidation of aqueous RB

It can be justified that suppression of OH• radicals takes place due to trapping of the conduction band electrons by the adsorbed metal ions and decreasing color removal might be expected [24]. Results indicated that significant decreasing in the initial degradation rate of photo-catalysis, is occurred in the presence of cations, among them Cu²⁺ has the largest effect (Figure 2). It can deduce that the retardation is due to Cu²⁺ ions, which it scavenges the electrons required for the formation of hydroxyl radicals. Results specified the Fe ions have an important role (increasing of % degradation) in the photo-degradation process which also has been reported by many researchers [25-27]. Fe⁺³ ions can accelerate the decomposition of many organic compounds in water using hydroxyl radicals formed in the following process [28].

This effect could be attributed to the scavenging of OH radicals by solvents or solubility of electrons, which are vital for generating OH radicals. If latter is the reason, one can expect higher degradation in more polar solvents than in less polar solvents. The dielectric constants of methanol and ethanol are 32.6 and 24.3, respectively. Therefore the possibility of generation OH radical in protic solvent like methanol is much higher compared to that of ethanol and consequently increases the rate of the degradation [29].

This is not surprising since excited electrons are less solvated in organic solvents than in aqueous solution. It may be that as the organic portion of the reaction mixture is increased, free electrons becomes less easily solvated, and the possibility of recombination with the positive hole (h⁺) increases. Another possibility is that the acetonitrile (and the other solvents examined) scavenge surface holes, which might be expected to retard photo-oxidation

[30,31].

As a result, solvent also can play a significant role in photo-degradation process. These effects are closely related to the nature and degree of the solute dipole moment changes in the process of solute solvent interactions [32]. In organic solvents, free electrons are less solvated and hence recombination of electron with hole is increased. Dye (RB) is zwitterionic form in neutral medium. Results specified that the degradation of dye in methanol is less than the others, this probably due to more solvation of dye in methanol. Since solvation can inhibit adsorption of dye on the surface of nano particles since solvation of dye in ethanol is less and hence degradation of dye in ethanol is more than methanol. Figure 3 presents the effect of solvents (Water, Ethanol and methanol) on the % degradation of RB by use TiO₂ and in present of 0.1 g/lit Titanium dioxide.

In previous studies, the effect of parameters such as pH, adsorbent amount and initial dye concentration and the adsorption of (RB) dye were carried out using sodium montmorillonite [16]. Results obtained from the present work specified that using TiO₂ nanoparticles, the photodegradation of RB is significantly.

Conclusion

Photo-degradation of (RB) using nanoparticle TiO₂ under UV light was investigated. The basis of reaction is photoredox process. Different parameters have important role in this process. Results showed that pH of the solution, type of solvent and the type of ions species can influence on dye degradation. The amount of pH solution changed the surface charge of TiO₂ particle. As a result, the adsorption of dye on the surface is altered thus causing a change in the reaction rate. In neutral medium, the adsorption of dye on the surface positively charged of TiO₂ is favourite, therefore % degradation of (RB) in this medium was the most amount. Adsorption of (RB) molecules on the surface of TiO₂ significantly changed in the presence of more amounts of the ionics in the normal, acidic and basic solutions so was influenced on the photo-bleaching of (RB) dye. Plus, in the normal solutions and in presence of the same amount of different salts, kind of salt was very important. Results indicated that significant decreasing in the initial degradation rate of photo-catalysis, is occurred in the presence of various cations, among them Cu²⁺ has largest effect but Fe⁺² increased photo degradation of (RB). Results indicated that, solvent also can play a significant role in variation of photo-physical properties in solutions, and results indicated that rate of % degradation in water is the highest amount between ethanol and methanol and water.

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